

Synthesis and Characterization of a Novel PMPAEMA-Br Macroinitiator

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Abstract

In this study, novel polymethacrylate derivate (PMPAEMA-Br macroinitiator) was synthesized by free radical polymerization reaction of 11-Bromoundec-1-ene and 2-(4-methoxyphenylamino)-2-oxoethyl methacrylate (MPAEMA). The chemical characterization of PMPAEMA-Br macroinitiator were determined by using spectroscopic methods such as proton magnetic resonance spectroscopy (¹H-NMR), carbon-13 magnetic resonance spectroscopy (¹³C-NMR) and fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR). The molecular weight and molecular weight distribution were determined by gel permeation chromatography (GPC). The synthesized novel PMPAEMA-Br will be applicable as macroinitiator in atom transfer radical polymerization (ATRP). The novel synthesized PMPAEMA-Br is considered to find potential application studies in ATRP polymerization as to be a suitable initiator.

Keywords: Methacrylate, 2-(4-methoxyphenylamino)-2-oxoethyl methacrylate, macroinitiator

1. Introduction

Research on controlled (living) free radical polymerization has considerably improved in the last years. (Braunecker and Matyjaszewski, 2007; Matyjaszewski and Spanswick, 2004; Zhang, 2013). These studies focus on living/controlled radical polymerization techniques such as nitroxide-mediated polymerization (NMP), atom transfer radical polymerization (ATRP) and reversible addition cleavage chain transfer polymerization (Kreutzer and Yagci, 2017; Matyjaszewski and Spanswick, 2004; Moad, et al., 2008, Nesvadba, 2013). The most important advantage of free radical polymerization is that many monomers (acrylates, methacrylates, vinyl monomers) can be polymerized using this method and this polymerization can be carried out under mild conditions (Coessens et al., 2001; Guerrero-Santos et al., 2013; Kostić et al., 2022; Yamada and Zetterlund, 2002). The most important disadvantage of free radical polymerization is that the polymer structure and molecular weight cannot be controlled and also polymers with large molecular weight distribution are produced (Chen et al., 2016; Shipp, 2005; Madruga, 2002; Zetterlund et al., 2015). In recent years, controlled radical polymerization techniques have made it possible to produce polymers with controlled molecular structure, controlled polymer weight and low molecular weight distribution (polydispersity). With controlled radical polymerization techniques, polymers with narrow molecular weight distribution can be produced at the desired molecular weight and in a controlled manner (Gentekos et al., 2019; Iwasaki and Yoshida 2005). Atom transfer radical polymerization (ATRP) is one of the most effective controlled living polymerization methods to obtain polymers and copolymers with different molecular structures (Coessens et al., 2001; Pan et al., 2018; Ran et al., 2014). ATRP polymerization can be used to synthesize polymers with various molecular structures such as block-copolymer brushes, star-like brushes and gradient brushes (Matahwa et al., 2011; Wang et al., 2023; Ren et al., 2016). Macroinitiators are a class of polymers with

functional groups that initiate further chain polymerizations such as radical, anionic and cationic polymerizations. Macroinitiators are generally polymers containing halogen as a functional group. Since polymerization proceeds from the targeted group, the polymeric unit in the macroinitiator is incorporated as a polymeric unit into the newly obtained polymer. Alkyl halides such as alkyl bromide and alkyl chloride are widely used as ATRP initiators (Matyjaszewski and Tsarevsky, 2014; Göktaş, 2019; Göktaş, 2020; Hazer et al., 2023; Inceoglu et al., 2004; Zhao et al., 2002). Methacrylate monomers/polymers are one of the most important commercial polymers with a wide range of applications. It is used in the production of many industrial materials such as unbreakable glasses, lighting housings and bathtubs (Pillai, 2010; Gandini and Lacerda, 2021). In the production of industrial materials with desired properties, acrylic monomers can be copolymerized with different monomers thanks to the different functional groups in their structure (Arshady, 1992; Rooney and Hutchinson 2018) In particular, studies have been directed towards the synthesis of polymers containing aminomethylmethacrylate monomers containing amine groups (Tan et al., 2025; Saputra et al., 2017). Due to their properties, different aminomethacrylate monomers can be used for the synthesis of polymeric membranes and chromatographic supports suitable for retention and separation in different fields such as wastewater treatment, solid phase extraction, protein recovery and purification, drug delivery systems and biochemical sensors (Groarke and Brabazon, 2016; Vlakh and Tennikova, 2009; Potter and Hilder, 2008). In this study, Firstly, the formula known the 2-(4-methoxyphenylamino)-2-oxoethyl methacrylate (MPAEMA) monomer was synthesized and characterized (Acikbas et al., 2016; Tanış et al., 2019) and then novel polymethacrylate derivate **PMPAEMA-Br** as macroinitiator was synthesized and characterized free radical polymerization reaction of 11-Bromoundec-1-ene and 2-(4-methoxyphenylamino)-2-oxoethyl methacrylate (MPAEMA) by using

Azo-bis-isobutyronitril (AIBN) as initiator by using classical spectroscopic methods (FTIR, $^1\text{H-NMR}$, $^{13}\text{C-NMR}$). The molecular weight of macroinitiator **PMPAEMA-Br** was determined by using gel permeation chromatography (GPC).

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Materials and instrumental measurements

The all chemicals (11-Bromoundec-1-ene, 4-methoxyaniline, chloroacetyl chloride, sodium acrylate, trimethylamine, azobisisobutyronitrile (AIBN)) and solvent 1,4 dioxane were procured from Sigma. FTIR spectra was performed on a Perkin Elmer Spectrum Two spectrophotometer equipped with ATR apparatus. The Bruker 400 MHz device was used for measuring the $^1\text{H-NMR}$ and $^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ spectra in DMSO solvent with the interior label of chemical shifts, tetramethyl silane. The molecular weight of the PMPAEMA-Br was determined by using gel permeation chromatography (GPC) on Aligent apparatus equipped with evaporative mass

detector, CHCl_3 solvent with polystyrene standards.

2.2. Synthesis of macroinitiators (PMPAEMA-Br)

2.2.1 Synthesis of 2-(2-methoxyphenylamino)-2-oxoethyl methacrylate (MPAEMA)

For the synthesis of formula known MPAEMA monomer, the compound 2-chloro-N-(4-methoxyphenyl) acetamide (1 mol) as refluxed in sodium methacrylate (1.2 mmol) 1,4-dioxane for 48 h using TEBAC-NaI as catalyst. Hydroquinone was used to prevent polymerization. At the end of the reaction time, the mixture was filtered to remove impurities. The mixture was washed with dilute base solution to remove the hydroquinone dissolved in the mixture (Acikbas et al., 2016; Tanış et al., 2019). MPAEMA was obtained in 85% yield. The synthesis reaction of MPAEMA has been shown in Figure 1. The all molecular structure data of MPAEMA obtained are in agreement with the literature (Acikbas et al., 2016; Tanış et al., 2019).

Figure 1. Synthesis of the MPAEMA monomer

2.2. Synthesis of PMPAEMA-Br macroinitiators

The **PMPAEMA-Br** macroinitiator was synthesized by free radical reaction of 1 mmol 2-(4-methoxyphenylamino)-2-oxoethylmethacrylate (MPAEMA) and 1 mmol 11-Bromoundec-1-ene dissolved in 10 ml 1,4-dioxane. The polymerization solution was carried out under inert Ar atmosphere at 70 °C for 72 hours using azobisisobutyronitrile

(AIBN) as a initiator. The **PMPAEMA-Br** was crystallized to remove impurities with ethyl alcohol. **PMPAEMA-Br** macroinitiator was dried under vacuum at room temperature. Synthesis of **PMPAEMA-Br** macroinitiator is shown in Figure 2. The chemical structure of **PMPAEMA-Br** was characterized spectroscopically by using FTIR, ¹H-NMR and ¹³C-NMR, and chromatographically by using GPC.

Figure 2. The synthesis of PMPAEMA-Br macroinitiator by free radical polymerization

Dark Yellow solid, Yield: 258.3 mg (65%). FT-IR (ATR, cm⁻¹) 3317 (-N-H), 1734 (-C=O ester), 1670 (-C=O amide), ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO) δ : 9.9 (1H, s, -NH), 7.47 (2H, d, J=9, ArH), 6.89-6.80 (2H, m, ArH), 4.74- 4.61 (2H, m, -OCH₂), 3.72-3.63 (3H, m, -OCH₃), 2.50 (s, -CH₂), 1.67-1.23 (3H, m, -CH₃).; ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, DMSO) δ : 166.2 (C, -C=O amide), 155.8 (C, -C=O ester), 132.2-114.3 (ArC), 68.5 (O=C-CH₂-O-), 55.6 (O-CH₃), 55.5 (-CH₂-Br), 23.7 (-CH₂), 21.2 (-CH₃).

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Synthesis and spectroscopic characterization of PMPAEMA-Br macroinitiator

The novel **PMPAEMA-Br** macroinitiator was synthesized by polymerization reaction of 2-(4-methoxyphenylamino)-2-oxoethylmethacrylate (MPAEMA) and 11-Bromoundec-1-ene (Figure 2.). The chemical structure of the **PMPAEMA-Br** macroinitiator was

determined by classical spectroscopic methods. The FTIR spectrum of **PMPAEAMA-Br** displayed -NH , -C=O (ester) and -C=O (amide) typical stretching bands at 3317, 1734 and 1670 cm^{-1} , respectively. (Figure 3.). In $^1\text{H-NMR}$ spectrum proton peaks at 9.9 ppm, 7.47 between 6.86 ppm were assigned to -NH group and aromatic -CH protons, respectively. In $^1\text{H-NMR}$ spectrum proton peaks at the low field signals at 2.50 ppm and 1.46 ppm were assigned to aliphatic -CH protons (Figure 4.). The $^1\text{H-NMR}$ spectrum of MPAEMA monomer had 5.9 and 5.6 ppm for =CH olefinic protons and these peaks have not been assigned to **PMPAEAMA-Br** $^1\text{H-NMR}$ spectrum. In the ^{13}C NMR spectrum, peaks of -C=O ester and -C=O amide were exhibited on 166.2 ppm and 155.8 ppm, respectively. The aromatic carbons were between 132.2 and 114.3 ppm. The aliphatic carbons were between 68.5 and 21.2 ppm. (Figure 5.). $^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ spectrum of

MPAEMA monomer had 135 ppm for $\text{CH}_3\text{-C=}$ and 127 ppm for =CH olefinic carbon atom but these peaks have not been assigned to **PMPAEAMA-Br** $^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ spectrum. For chromatographic characterization of **PMPAEAMA-Br** macroinitiator, molecular weight distribution and molecular weight of macroinitiator were investigated by GPC. The highest molecular weight of the **PMPAEAMA-Br** macroinitiator [weight-average molecular weight (M_w) = 1810, number-average molecular weight (M_n) = 2542] was determined, and polydispersity index (PDI) of **PMPAEAMA-Br** macroinitiator (M_w/M_n) = 1.403 was detected by GPC based on polystyrene standards. All the data shown that **PMPAEAMA-Br** macroinitiator successfully synthesized 11-Bromoundec-1-ene with MPAEMA via free radical route.

Figure 3. The FTIR spectrum of PMPAEAMA-Br macroinitiator

Figure 4. The $^1\text{H-NMR}$ spectrum of PMPAEAMA-Br macroinitiator

Figure 5. The ^{13}C -NMR spectrum of PMPAEAMA-Br macroinitiator

3. Conclusions

In this study, the novel polymethacrylate derivate (**PMPAEAMA-Br** macroinitiator) was synthesized by free radical polymerization and characterized by using classical spectroscopic methods (FTIR, ^1H -NMR, ^{13}C -NMR). The molecular weight of macroinitiator was determined by using gel permeation chromatography (GPC). The novel synthesized **PMPAEAMA-Br** is considered to find potential application studies in ATRP polymerization as to be a suitable initiator. This new polymethacrylate derivative with **PMPAEAMA-Br** macroinitiator is expected to provide a new perspective for research in the field of ATRP.

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